

Analysis of Discriminant Model on Marketing Mix Against the Decision of Buying Traditional Weaving Handicraft Products of Karo District

Nurafrina Siregar

Lecturer at Social Science Faculty, Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Medan, Indonesia, 20122

ABSTRACT

This research aims to know the function of discrimination and to know the level of precision marketing classification mix against the decision of purchasing products traditional weaving fabric Karo district. The interest rate of local and international buyers is very low due to the expensive price and the effort of obtaining raw materials such as yarn research method used in this study is a descriptive explorative. According to Usman (Usman, 2009) that any research is definitely descriptive (clarifying), then this research includes a descriptive research-exploratory. This research was conducted to test the hypothesis proposed using the research methods that have been designed in accordance with the variables examined in order to obtain accurate results. This research-based discriminant analysis. Result of discriminant function accuracy of marketing mix to purchase decision of traditional weaving fabric of Karo district.

Keywords: Marketing Mix, Purchase Decision

INTRODUCTION

Anciently with limited tools and materials and a low level of human resources, humans formed a garment of bark. Because it feels less comfortable wearing clothes from the bark, the clothes from the bark of wood can cause itching and damage to the skin then the ancestors began to look for another alternative that makes the basic material cotton. So since then comes the clothes from weaving ikat from various regions.

Karo traditional clothing is certainly one of the results of the Karo culture,

therefore, as the development of culture, Karo people have many varieties of clothing with different functions. Traditionally this outfit was in weaving by the Karo women using a kembaya (a kind of cotton) that is used as yarn and dyed with dye tools made from lime, kitchen ash, turmeric, and telep (a kind of plant). Around the system and motif of ikat weaving, he pointed out the possibility that the cultural structure of Kewapante society is generally based on the principle of pairs of men and women.

Based on this idea, studied motif-motifs and various geometric ornaments from the weaving of ikat, in the area of Samosir precisely motifs and various geometric ornamental aspects of this culture is the art of weaving of ikat. As two integrated elements into one organism. From the existence of this partner system, the truth is that the traditional weaving of Karo district as part of local and from integral Indonesian nation is directed to colleagues, as Friends Life and work opponents. It is also obvious that traditional weaving motifs in general the traditional Karo clothing can be divided into three groups, namely: day-to-day attire, party attire, and oversized clothes.

Clothing commonly used men are garments with a model of Chinese long-sleeved stone scissors, the lid is called Tengkuluk or Reed and sarongs, while for women consist of the shirt of the round neck, sarong (abit), headgear (hood), and a custom cloth named Uis Gara that is spread and precisely displays personality or self identity. Local wisdom culture promoted by

the people of Karo district experienced many weaknesses with a price that is quite expensive because of the raw materials that can be from outside the area such as yarn and woven fabrics that are ready so hard to market in because competitiveness price is quite expensive if compared with woven fabrics that come from outside the area. With this research how does the discriminant function on marketing mix against the decision of purchasing the traditional weaving fabrics of Karo district and how the accuracy of the marketing classification of the mix to purchase decisions of traditional weaving fabrics Karo district.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Marketing

According to Kotler and Keller (2012:5) marketing a societal process in which individuals and groups acquire what they need and want to create, offer, and freely exchange products and services of value with others, while according to Abdullah and Tantri (2012:14) marketing a social and managerial process whereby individuals and groups get their needs and desires by creating, offering and exchanging something worth each other.

Marketing Management is an analysing activity, planning, implementation, and control of programs that are made to establish, build, and maintain, profit from the exchange through the target market to achieve the objectives of the Organization (the company) in the long term. (Assauri, 2015:12). Based on the understanding of marketing management of the two experts above can be concluded that, marketing management is an activity process in which there is analysis, planning, implementation of ideas, pricing, promoting goods and services to create and maintain exchanges to benefit from the target market to achieve or satisfy the objectives of individuals and organizations.

2. Marketing Strategy

To sustain a company's survival in achieving the company's goals and vision,

every company needs a marketing strategy. There are many marketing strategies that can be applied in a company one of them is the marketing mix. The right marketing strategy can be used to capitalize on existing opportunities so that the company can thrive and survive the market. Planning a product marketing strategy can provide a basis for the company to take effective steps for a period of time.

3. Marketing Mix

In marketing, there is one strategy called Marketing mix. The marketing mix becomes one of the most important strategies that companies use to influence consumer buying decisions on a product or service. Of these three theories concluded that the marketing mix is a set of tools and tactics that can be used to determine the level of marketing success for the company. In the marketing mix, there are elements of variables that mutually support one another. According to Kotler and Keller (2013:25) variables in the marketing mix are grouped into four, namely product (product), price (prices), place (place), promotion (promotion), and physical evidence.

a) Product

The product is the first element and is one of the most important elements of the marketing mix. According to Kotler and Keller (2012:170) The product is anything that can be offered to the market to satisfy a desire or need, including physical goods, services, experiences, events, people, places, properties, organizations, information, and ideas. The product has several indicators so that consumers can determine what kind of products they want. Here's an explanation of each product indicator:

- Product Quality
- Variety (variety)
- Features (features)
- Product Design
- Brand
- Packaging
- Services (Product Support Services)

b) Price

Price is one of the elements of the marketing mix and is an element that provides income for the company's finances. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2014:312), the price is the amount of money to be paid to get a product or service. Meanwhile, according to Gitosudarmono (in Sunyoto, 2013:131), the price is actually a value expressed in one currency or an exchange, against a particular product. According to Kotler & Armstrong (2014:76) There are several price indicators. Here's an explanation of price indicators:

1. List price is information on the price of products offered to consumers.
2. Discount (discount) is the discounted price given to the consumer.
3. Special Discount (allowance) is the price of discount offered to consumers during certain events.
4. Payment period is a payment made during maturity date.
5. Credit terms are payments made continuously within a certain period of time.

c) Place (Place/Distribution Channel)

According to Kotler & Keller (2016:516), distribution channels are interdependent organisations that are covered in processes that make products or services available for use or consumption. Meanwhile, according to Stern & El-Ansary in Abdullah & Tantri (2012:207) states that "marketing channels can be seen as a group of organizations that are interdependent with each other involved in the process of providing a product or service for use or consumption.

d) Promotion

Definition of promotion according to Kotler & Armstrong (2014:76) That promotion refers to activities that communicate the benefits of the product and persuade the target customer to make a purchase of the product produced. According to Stanton in Sunyoto (2013:154) It states that, promotion is an element in the marketing mix of companies that are covedable to inform, persuade, and remind about the company's products. According to Kotler & Armstrong

(2014:429), there are five elements of promotional mix to communicate value to customers i.e. advertising, sales promotion, personal sales, public relations, and direct marketing.

1) Advertising

According to Hermawan (2012:72) Advertising or advertising is a form of presentation and non-personal promotion of ideas, goods or services performed by certain companies. Kotler in Hermawan (2012:73) underlined advertising objectives in three main categories:

- a. Provide information (to notify), in this case convey to the consumer about a new product.
- b. Persuading (to persuade), in this case encouraging prospective consumers to switch on different products.
- c. Remind (to remind), in this case remind the buyer where they can obtain a product.

2) Sales Promotion

Sales promotions are a range of short-term incentives to drive purchases or sales of products or services. Includes discounts, coupons, performances, exhibitions, demonstrations and others.

- a. Personal selling
- b. Public relations
- c. Direct Marketing

4. Purchase Decisions

The purchase decision is the fourth stage of the decision making process. Before the purchase decision stage, consumers have already done three steps first: Introduction to problems, information retrieval, and evaluation of alternatives.

According to Kotler (2007:223) The purchase decision is several steps taken by the consumer before making a product purchase decision. According to Setiadi in Sangadji and Sopiah (2013:121) The essence of the consumer decision-making is the integration process that combines the knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors, and chooses one of them.

5. Marketing Mix To Purchase Decision

The marketing mix strategy formed by the company became one of the factors affecting the consumer buying decision on a product offered by the company. Kotler and Armstrong (2014:76) have been finalized that the marketing mix is a collection of controlled tactical marketing tools combined with the company to produce the response it wants to market.

METHODS

The research method used in this study is descriptive explorative. Any research is definitely descriptive (clarifying), then this research includes a descriptive research-exploratory (Usman, 2009). This research was conducted to test the hypothesis proposed using the research methods that have been designed in accordance with the variables examined in order to obtain accurate results. This research-based discriminant analysis. The population is a generalization area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics established by researchers to be studied and then withdrawn in conclusion (Sugiyono, 2014).

In this research the population technique taken all the traditional weaving cloth in the indigenous Karo district. The method used is discriminant analysis. The main uses of discriminant analysis are two.

First is the ability to predict the occurrence of dependent variables with independent variable inputs. Second is the ability to choose where independent variables that typically real affect dependent and safe variables that are not (Santoso, 2010). Steps conducting discriminant analysis is as follows:

The discriminant analysis Model is an equation that demonstrates a linear combination of various independent variables:

$$D = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + \dots + b_kx_k$$

To distinguish respondents in which classes can use optimum cutting score. For disproportionate samples (the number of members of the two groups are different), the cutting score is expressed with the formula:

$$Z_{cu} = \frac{Z_A N_A + Z_B N_B}{N_A + N_B}$$

RESULT

1. Validity and Reliability Testing

a) Validity testing

To know the eligibility of the items in the poll list that has been presented to the respondent, a validity test is required. If the validity of any question is greater (>) 0.30, then the question item is considered valid.

Table 1 Validity Test (X1) Product

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Statement X1.1	13.2167	6.606	.304	.691
Statement X1.2	13.3000	6.888	.418	.778
Statement X1.3	13.6167	7.885	.549	.657
Statement X1.4	13.6000	8.261	.441	.871
Statement X1.5	13.8333	8.800	.571	.770

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 2 Validity Test (X2) Price

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Statement X2.1	13.2583	5.790	.360	.769
Statement X2.2	13.3583	4.988	.564	.702
Statement X2.3	13.7000	5.573	.640	.745
Statement X2.4	13.3417	5.034	.471	.735
Statement X2.5	13.3083	5.307	.448	.742

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 3 Validity Test (X₃) Place

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Statement X3.1	14.1000	11.982	.551	.689
Statement X3.2	15.7000	12.676	.609	.727
Statement X3.3	13.3917	10.978	.397	.686
Statement X3.4	15.6500	13.441	.658	.675
Statement X3.5	14.3250	12.381	.529	.545

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 4 Validity Test (X₄) Promotion

Item-Total Statistics				
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Statement X4.1	11.9083	7.791	.555	.610
Statement X4.2	12.3167	8.975	.530	.737
Statement X4.3	12.1833	7.356	.762	.668
Statement X4.4	12.1833	7.674	.647	.689
Statement X4.5	11.9417	7.628	.467	.737

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 5 Reliability Test (X₁) Product

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.798	5

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 9 Reliability Test (Y) Purchase Decisions

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.859	5

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 6 Reliability Test (X₂) Price

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.798	5

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 7 Reliability Test (X₃) Place

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.764	5

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Table 8 Reliability Test (X₄) Promotion

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.782	5

Source : SPSS Processing result version 16.0

2. Testing The Classic Assumption

a. Test data normality

Test normality aims to test whether in a regression, disruptor variable or residual distribution is normal or not. A regression Model is either normal data distribution or close to normal.

Histogram

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Normal P-P Plot of Regression Standardized Residual

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Figure 1 Histogram Test Normality

The multicollinearity test of the poll that has been distributed to the Respoden can be seen in the table below.

Table 10 Multicholinerity Test

Coefficients ^a		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
Model		B	Std. Error			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-1.227	.751	-1.635	.105		
	Product	.087	.058	2.512	.033	.259	3.857
	Price	.328	.075	4.355	.000	.239	4.187
	Place	.140	.038	3.637	.000	.398	2.511
	Promotion	.370	.065	5.699	.000	.214	4.665
	People	.161	.054	2.964	.004	.332	3.009
	Physical Evidence	.041	.037	2.119	.026	.565	1.769
	Process	.071	.063	2.142	.026	.240	4.164

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

b. Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test aims to test whether in regression model there is variance inequality from the residual of one observation to another observation. A good regression Model is one that does not happen to Heteroskedasticity.

Scatterplot

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Figure 2 Scatterplot of Heteroskedasticity Test

3. Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regression aims at calculating the influence of two or more free variables against one bound variable and predicting a bound variable using two or more free variables. The formula of multiple regression analyses as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + b_7X_7$$

Table 11 Multiple Linear Regression

Coefficients ^a							
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-1.677	.751	-1.635	.105		
	Product	.056	.053	2.412	.013	.249	3.547
	Price	.258	.074	4.355	.000	.219	4.257
	Place	.120	.035	3.437	.000	.368	2.261
	Promotion	.350	.063	5.799	.000	.254	4.565

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Based on the table 4.62 is obtained multiple linear regression as follows:

$$Y = -1.667 + 0.056 X_1 + 0.258 X_2 + 0.120 X_3 + 0.350 X_4$$

The way that is used is to look at the level of significant (= 0.05). If the value of significance is smaller than 0.05 then H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted.

Table 12 Simultaneous Test

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1134.774	7	162.111	126.834	.000^a
	Residual	143.151	112	1.278		
	Total	1277.925	119			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Process, Place, Physical Evidence, Promotion, People, Product, Price

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

a. Partial Significant Test (Test T)

A partial test (t) shows how far free variables individually explain the variation of the test performed using a 5% significance rate.

Table 13 Partial Test

Coefficients ^a					
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error		
1	(Constant)	-1.227	.731	-1.545	.105
	Product	.054	.048	2.452	.013
	Price	.328	.065	4.265	.000
	Place	.127	.028	3.677	.000
	Promotion	.357	.045	5.599	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

b. Coefficient of Determination

This analysis of coefficient of determination is used to determine the percentage of magnitude of variable influence free of bound variables.

Table 14 Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.998 ^a	.888	.878	1.11034

a. Predictors: (Constant), Process, Place, Physical Evidence, Promotion, People, Product, Price

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Decision

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

c. Discriminant Analysis

	Function
	1
Promotion	.911
Price	.909
Place	.560
Produk ^a	.531
Pooled within-groups correlations between discriminating variables and standardized canonical discriminant functions Variables ordered by absolute size of correlation within function.	
a. This variable not used in the analysis.	

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Test of Function(s)	Wilks' Lambda	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	.486	84.342	2	.000

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

According to the Table 16, Wilk's Lambda is known for the significance of the Chi-square statistics value of 0.000 (< 0.05) which means there is a significant difference between the two groups of respondents based on the free variables.

	Function
	1
Price	.253
Promotion	.208
(Constant)	-6.870
Unstandardized coefficients	

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

According to Table 17, canonical's Discriminant Function Coefficients above shows the discriminant function with the following equation: Z score = -6.870 (constant) + 0.253 X1 + 0.208 X2. This function is useful for analyzing the case or the respondents studied will belong to the group, i.e. the first group (decision 0) or second (decision 1).

Purchase Decision	Function
	1
0	-1.717
1	.501
Unstandardized canonical discriminant functions evaluated at group means	

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Based on table 18, there are two distinct groups of groups with a decision of 0 with a negative centroid (average group) and a group of decision 1 with a positive centroid (average group).

Processed	110	
Excluded	Missing or out-of-range group codes	0
	At least one missing discriminating variable	0
Used in Output	110	

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Keputusan Pembelian	Prior	Cases Used in Analysis	
		Unweighted	Weighted
0	.500	36	36.000
1	.500	85	85.000
Total	1.000	120	120.000

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Prior Probabilities for Groups showed the group with a degree of 0 as many as 31 samples while the group with a decision of 1 to 85 sample.

	Purchase Decision	
	0	1
Price	2.752	3.465
Promotion	.271	.78
(Constant)	-21.599	-38.445
Fisher's linear discriminant functions		

Source: SPSS Processing result version 16.0

Based on table Table 21, the Classification Function Coefficients shows the same thing as the Canonical linear Function Coefficients above that was previously discussed. The similarities are as follows:

- A. For group 0, the similarities:
Value = -21,599 (constant) + 2.752 (X1) + 0.271 (X2)
- B. For group 1, the similarities:
Value = -38,445 (constant) + 3.465 (X1) + 0.758 (X2)

DISCUSSION

1. Effect Of Product On Purchasing Decision

The results showed a significant 0.013 < 0.05, so Ha received and H0 was rejected, stating a partially significant effect

on the purchase decision. The study stated that product quality is the ability of a product to perform its functions, including durability, reliability, accuracy, ease, operation and repair and other attributes. "The more quality a product, the higher the consumer decision to buy or not to buy a product.

2. Price Influence On Purchasing Decisions

The results showed and were significant $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a received and H_0 were rejected, stating the price was partially significant to the purchase decision. The study stated that price is the value of goods expressed with money. In a company determining prices on products is very important. In determining the price must be appropriate to cover all costs or even more charges to get a profit or profit. However, if pricing on the product is too high it can result in reduced gains. With this consumer or buyer will be reduced, sales charts will be reduced, all costs that have been used will not be fulfilled or not covered, the company will suffer losses.

3. Place Effect On Purchasing Decisions

The results showed a significant $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a was accepted and H_0 rejected, stating place a partial significant effect on the purchasing decision. The study stated that a place is one of the important factors or aspects in determining purchasing decisions. If you want to open an effort in the business world, the location must be strategic that aims to determine the purpose of the business entity of the company. The location makes consumers can make a buying decision or not to buy a product. With ease to find the location, easy access to the location, especially with the large percir area, especially the place that the layout is good, fill consumers comfortable and can determine the decision to buy.

4. Promotion Effect On Purchasing Decisions

The results showed a significant $0.000 < 0.05$, so H_a received and H_0 rejected, which declared promotion a partial significant effect on the purchasing

decision. The study stated that promotion has a significant impact on purchasing decisions. Purchasing decisions are an important factor in determining whether a buyer determines a purchase decision or does not purchase a product. A company must conduct promotions to introduce its products to the wider community. People will never know if the company does not promote its products. In addition to introducing products, promotion is used to convey information about product benefits and also persuade customers to buy products.

CONCLUSION

1. Product significant positive effect is partial to the decision of purchasing significant value $0.013 < 0.05$.
2. Price significant positive effect and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Place significant positive effect of the significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$. Promotion has a significant positive effect and a significant value of $0.000 < 0.05$.

REFERENCES

1. Adiwarmarman Karim, Ekonomi Islam, Jakarta: Gema Insani, 2001.
2. Amirullah, Pengantar Bisnis, Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu, 2005.
3. Arikunto Sugiyono, Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2012.
4. Arikunto Suharsimi, Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Pratek, edisi revisi 1V, Yogyakarta: Rineka Cipta, 1998.
5. Ghozali Imam, Aplikasi Analisis Multivariati Dengan Program SPSS.
6. Ginting Nembah F. Hartimbul, Manajemen Pemasaran, Jilid I, Bandung: Yrama Widya, 2011.
7. Gitosudarmono, Manajemen Pemasaran, Yogyakarta: BPFE UGM, 2000.
8. Hakim Lukman, Prinsip - prinsip Ekonomi Islam, Surakarta: Erlangga, 2012.
9. Hapsari Niken Tri, Seluk Beluk Promosi dan Bisnis, Jogjakarta: Aplus Books, 2010.
10. Husein Umar, Metode Penelitian untuk Skripsi dan Tesis Bisnis, Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada, 2005.

11. Husein Umar, *Research Methods in Finance and Banking*, Jakarta: PT Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2000.
12. Kartajaya Hermawan, *Marketing Mix*, Bandung: Mizan Pustaka, 2006.
13. Kasmir, *Kewirausahaan*, Jakarta: Rajawali, 2014. Kartajaya et al, *Marketing Syariah*, Jakarta: Gema Insani Press, 2008.
14. Kotler Philip, et al. *Principles of Marketing*, 10th edition: Pearson Education International, 2004.
15. Kotler Philip, *Marketing Management*, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 2001.
16. Kottler Philip. (ed.). *Manajemen Pemasaran di Indonesia*, diadaptasi oleh A.B. Susanto dari "Marketing Management". Jakarta: Salemba
17. Rangkuti Feddy, *Marketing Analysis Made Easy*, Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama, 2005.
18. Rismiati Catur, *Pemasaran Barang dan Jasa*, Yogyakarta, Kanisius: 2001.
19. Rivai Veithzal, *Islamic Marketing (Membangun dan Mengembangkan Bisnis dengan Praktik Marketing Rasulullah saw)*, Jakarta: Gramedia, 2012.
20. Sarjono Hariadi, et al, *SPSS vs LISREL Sebuah Pengantar Aplikasi Untuk Riset*, Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2011.
21. SK Purwanto, dan Suharyadi, *Statistik Untuk Ekonomi dan Kuangan Modern*, Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2004.
22. Sugiono, *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R & D*, Bandung: Alfabeta, 2008.
23. Suharsimi, *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Pratek*, edisi revisi 1V, Yogyakarta: Rineka Cipta, 1998.
24. Suryani Tatik, *Perilaku Konsumen*, Yogyakarta: Graha Ilmu, 2008.
25. Tjiptono Fandy, *Strategi Pemasaran*, Edisi Kedua, Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi, 1997.
26. Sarjono Hariadi dan Winda Julianita, *SPSS vs LISREL Sebuah Pengantar Aplikasi Untuk Riset*, Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2011.
27. Siregar Syofian, *Statistik Deskriptif untuk Penelitian Dilengkapi Perhitungan Manual dan Aplikasi SPSS Versi 17*, Jakarta: Rajawali Pers, 2010. Suharyadi et al, *Statistika untuk Ekonomi dan Keuangan Modern*, Jakarta: Salemba Empat, 2004.
28. Swasta Basu, *Manajemen Pemasaran (Analisa Perilaku Konsumen)*, Yogyakarta: BPFE UGM, 2000.

How to cite this article: Siregar N. Analysis of discriminant model on marketing mix against the decision of buying traditional weaving handicraft products of Karo district. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2020; 7(6): 192-201.
